

POTENTIAL ANALGESICS. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED 4-QUINAZOLONES

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Using the concept of quarternary carbon and tertiary nitrogen in β -relationship to each other in a molecule, as an optimal and perhaps an essential feature of potent analgesics, seventeen substituted 4-quinazolones have been synthesised as intermediates in the preparation of substituted 4-quinazolinols and their esters for testing their analgesic activity.

A comparative study of the structures of morphine, pethidine and methadone reveals that the only feature common to all these, is the presence of the tertiary nitrogen atom and a quarternary carbon in β -relationship to it. Using the concept of quarternary carbon and tertiary nitrogen in β -relationship to each other, as an optimal and perhaps an essential feature of potent analgesics (Eddy, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1950, 39, 247) work has been undertaken to synthesise substituted 4-quinazolones having two tertiary nitrogen atoms in their molecule and also to change them into 4-quinazolinols and their esters which would, in addition, have a quarternary carbon in β -relationship to one of the tertiary nitrogen atoms. Both these groups of compounds will be tested for their analgesic activity.

As a first step, the present paper reports the preparation of some substituted 4-quinazolones obtained by the general method worked out by Grimmel, Guenther and Morgan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 542) by condensing *N*-acetyl-, *N*-*n*-propionyl- or *N*-*n*-butyryl-anthranilic acid with aniline, *ortho*-, *meta*- or *para*-toluidine, *ortho*- or *para*-nitroaniline or α - or β -naphthylamine in the presence of phosphorus trichloride (cf. Sen and Sidhu, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 437; Sen and Upadhyaya, *ibid.*, 1950, 27, 40). *N*-acetylanthranilic acid was prepared by the action of acetic anhydride on anthranilic acid, suspended in benzene (Kauffmann, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 3482). *N*-*n*-Propionyl- and *N*-*n*-butyryl-anthranilic acids were obtained by the oxidation of the corresponding *N*-substituted *o*-toluidines with potassium permanganate (cf. Pictet and Duparc, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 3421). The method has been worked out in detail and quantitative yields of these acids have been obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-*n*-Propionylantranilic Acid.—*N*-*n*-Propionyl-*o*-toluidine (15 g.) was oxidised by heating with potassium permanganate (60 g.) in a litre of water in a 2-litre flask over a steam bath. The permanganate was added in two equal lots, the second lot being added only when the first one was completely used up. After decolorisation of the second lot was complete (4-6 hours), the manganese dioxide formed was filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated to a small volume, cooled in ice and acidified with cold concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitated acid was collected on a Buchner funnel, washed with a small quantity of ice-cold water and dried, yield 15 g. (nearly quantitative). On recrystallisation from hot water it gave white needles, m. p. 116-117°.

N-n-Butyrylanthranilic Acid.—*N-n-Butyryl-o-toluidine* (15 g.) was oxidised with 60 g. of potassium permanganate exactly as above, yield 14.5 g. (nearly quantitative). It was redissolved in cold dilute sodium carbonate and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid as white needles, m.p. 109-10° (Heilbron and Bunbury reported m.p. as 89°, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Vol. I, 1946, p. 167). (Found: N, 6.56. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$: N, 6.76 per cent).

2-R₁-3-R₂-4-Quinazolone: General Procedure.—In a three-necked 500 c.c. flask, fitted with a reflux condenser, a dropping funnel and a mechanical stirrer, 0.05 mole *N*-acylanthranilic acid was covered with 0.05 mole of pure R₂-amine, dissolved in 80 c.c. of dry toluene. Phosphorus trichloride (0.017*M*) in 12 c.c. of dry toluene was added dropwise during the course of 15 minutes. The contents of the flask were then refluxed for 2 hours in an oil-bath at 130°-135°. The stir ring must be efficient, otherwise, a thick mass settles at the bottom and the yield is lowered. The reaction mixture

TABLE I

Reactants	2-R ₁ -3-R ₂ -4-Quinazolone.	M. p. of base.	M. p. of hydrochloride.	Yield.	Formula.	Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.
A and <i>o</i> -toluidine	R ₁ = methyl-; R ₂ = <i>o</i> -tolyl-	115-16°	248-50°	48%	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂	11.45%	11.20%
A and <i>m</i> -toluidine	R ₁ = methyl-; R ₂ = <i>m</i> -tolyl-	126°	250-52°	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂	11.68	11.20
B and aniline	R ₁ = ethyl-; R ₂ = phenyl-	126-27°	212-14°	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂	10.80	11.20
B and <i>o</i> -toluidine	R ₁ = ethyl-; R ₂ = <i>o</i> -tolyl-	94-95°	195-96°	49	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ON ₂	10.37	10.60
B and <i>m</i> -toluidine	R ₁ = ethyl-; R ₂ = <i>m</i> -tolyl-	131-32°	211-12°	53	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ON ₂	10.41	10.60
B and <i>p</i> -toluidine	R ₁ = ethyl-; R ₂ = <i>p</i> -tolyl-	162-63°	218-20°	74	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ON ₂	10.40	10.60
B and <i>o</i> -nitroaniline	R ₁ = ethyl-; R ₂ = <i>o</i> -nitro-phenyl-	167-68°	193-95°	71	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	13.83	14.27
B and <i>p</i> -nitroaniline	R ₁ = ethyl-; R ₂ = <i>p</i> -nitro-phenyl-	194-95°	223-24°	71	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	13.70	14.27
B and α -naphthyl-amine	R ₁ = ethyl-; R ₂ = α -naphthyl-	143-44°	214-16°	71	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ON ₂	9.40	9.33
B and β -naphthyl-amine	R ₁ = ethyl-; R ₂ = β -naphthyl-	138-39°	194-95°	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ON ₂	8.93	9.33
C and <i>o</i> -aniline	R ₁ = <i>n</i> -propyl-; R ₂ = phenyl-	120-21°	202-3°	67	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ON ₂	10.82	10.60
C and <i>o</i> -toluidine	R ₁ = <i>n</i> -propyl-; R ₂ = <i>o</i> -tolyl-	Sticky solid	199-200	52*	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ON ₂ HCl	9.21†	8.90†
C and <i>m</i> -toluidine	R ₁ = <i>n</i> -propyl-; R ₂ = <i>m</i> -tolyl-	80-81°	176-77°	54	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ON ₂	9.68	10.07
C and <i>p</i> -toluidine	R ₁ = <i>n</i> -propyl-; R ₂ = <i>p</i> -tolyl-	144-45°	176-77°	54	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ON ₂	10.57	10.07
C and <i>o</i> -nitroaniline	Original amine recovered	—	—	—	—	—	—
C and <i>p</i> -nitroaniline	R ₁ = <i>n</i> -propyl-; R ₂ = <i>p</i> -nitro-phenyl-	159-60°	191-93°	76	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃	13.91	13.59†
C and α -naphthyl-amine	R ₁ = <i>n</i> -propyl-; R ₂ = α -naphthyl-	131-32°	—	64	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ON ₂	8.40	8.91
C and β -naphthyl-amine	R ₁ = <i>n</i> -propyl-; R ₂ = β -naphthyl-	126-27°	187-88°	64	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ON ₂	9.23	8.91

A = *N*-Acetylanthranilic acid. B = *N-n*-Propionylanthranilic acid. C = *N-n*-Butyrylanthranilic acid

* As hydrochloride

† Based on hydrochloride.

was then transferred to a larger flask and made alkaline with 10% solution of sodium carbonate (about 100 c.c.) and the toluene removed by steam distillation. After cooling, the supernatant liquid was either filtered or decanted off. The products formed, starting with aniline, *p*-toluidine or *o*- or *p*-nitroaniline, solidified at this stage and were collected on a Buchner funnel. Others, formed from *o*- or *m*-toluidine or α - or β -naphthylamine, were semi-solid and were isolated as solids after triturating it with a little alcohol or as crystalline hydrochlorides by passing dry hydrogen chloride in an alcoholic or ethereal solution of the semi-solid product. The bases were regenerated by treating the hydrochlorides with cold dilute ammonia and recrystallised from dilute alcohol. The hydrochlorides of all other bases were also prepared as described above. The data about quinazolones, thus prepared, are given in Table I.

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